

MODERN ASPECTS AND METHODS OF TREATMENT OF CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS

Khakimova S. Z.

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor, Department of Neurology, Faculty of Postgraduate Education

Qodirov U. A.

Assistant Doctor of Medical Sciences, Department of Neurology, Faculty of Postgraduate Education, Samarkand Medical University, Samarkand. Uzbekistan

Abstract: Osteochondrosis is a disease of the musculoskeletal system manifested by thinning of bones and cartilage of joints. Patients are most commonly diagnosed with osteochondrosis of the spine, in which there is destruction of the intervertebral discs in the cervical, lumbar, or thoracic region. Intervertebral cartilage is necessary to cushion movements and reduce the load on bone tissue, so the destruction of discs leads to gradual damage to the vertebrae and deformation of the spine. Osteochondrosis can be a complication of trauma, long-term violation of posture or other pathological condition. Treatment of the disease involves manual therapy, physiotherapy and surgical interventions for significant spinal deformities.

Key words: osteochondrosis, spinal deformities, cervical spine.

Introduction. Modern sedentary lifestyle is the reason why such a common disease as cervical osteochondrosis is actively getting younger. It is increasingly being complained about by 'IT workers', drivers and other representatives of 'sedentary' professions. According to medics, even 17-year-old teenagers complain of cervical osteochondrosis. As a rule, these are those who actively use a smartphone. The fact is that depending on the inclination over the gadget, the human spine experiences a load from 12 to 27 kg. The more time a person spends in this position, the faster the intervertebral discs wear out, neck and back pain occurs, and then osteochondrosis. Doctors strongly recommend starting treatment immediately at the appearance of the first symptoms, otherwise the consequences of neglecting your health can be irreversible. The most mobile of all the spine is the cervical spine. It has seven vertebrae that are connected by elastic intervertebral discs. Each disc has a fibrous ring with a pulposus nucleus inside. Disturbance in its metabolism can indicate the appearance of osteochondrosis, in which the intervertebral disc loses its strength and elasticity. Subsequently, under the influence of loading, the fibrous ring bulges, cracks occur on it. The cervical region has many nerve channels and blood vessels to nourish the brain, and the vertebrae are closely adjacent to each other. Thus, even a moderate deformation of one of the vertebrae causes nerve structures and blood vessels to become compressed. The first signs of the disease manifest themselves in the form of tension and tingling sensations in the muscles of the neck, painful sensations that can recoil in the area of the back of the head, shoulder blades, arms. When, due to osteochondrosis, cerebral circulation is disturbed, migraines, vegetovascular diseases, hypertension appear. Also, the disease has a bad effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems, general coordination, hearing and vision deteriorate. If you do not start treatment in time, cervical osteochondrosis can become the cause of intervertebral protrusion, hernia, spinal artery syndrome.

Diagnosis of cervical osteochondrosis

Diagnosis and treatment of osteochondrosis of the cervical spine is carried out by narrowly focused specialists - orthopedists-traumatologists and neurologists specialising in the field of vertebrology. First of all, the doctor determines the degree of severity of the symptoms of the disease. Possible

causes of appearance are also determined - harmful working conditions, the patient's habits, the presence of injuries. If necessary, the patient is recommended additional examination:

X-ray shows the degree of instability of the vertebral bodies of the cervical department.

MRI allows you to identify the formation of protrusions, herniated intervertebral discs and the condition of soft tissues. Ultrasound of the vessels of the head and cervical department (Dopplerography) is recommended in disorders of cerebral circulation, migraines. This examination allows you to determine the condition of vertebral arteries, veins, as well as the presence of pathological tortuosity and loops of vessels. Ultrasound also allows you to see violations of vascular patency. In combination, all these examinations allow you to see the overall picture of the state of the cervical spine to correctly establish a diagnosis and prescribe the most effective treatment and further rehabilitation to consolidate the long-term result.

Treatment is aimed at improving blood supply to the brain and tissues surrounding the cervical spine, increasing the mobility of blocked segments of the cervical spine, reducing pain and myotonic syndrome. Various techniques are used to achieve these goals:

Massages in combination with light orthopedic corrections to improve blood flow in the cervical spine. The short lever method for spinal correction. This non-traumatic method allows you to effectively eliminate functional blocks and restore the mobility of segments. Shockwave therapy to improve metabolic processes, cell renewal and affected tissue areas, and eliminate muscle spasms. Carboxytherapy (the therapeutic effect of carbon dioxide on the tissues of the spine and joints). Physiotherapy methods of treatment (electrotherapy and magnetotherapy). Drug treatment (blockades, multizonal and other injections) in combination with the above methods. Medications are used only in certain cases, to relieve an acute condition with myotonic (soft tissue edema) and pain syndrome.

Physical therapy for osteochondrosis of the cervical spine

Physical therapy is becoming increasingly popular in the treatment of diseases. It is used not only in remission, but also as a prophylaxis of cervical osteochondrosis. Physical exercises improve blood circulation, strengthen the muscular corset, eliminate restrictions on the mobility of the vertebrae, increase the volume of movements, and allow you to restore neuromuscular connections. In the course of comprehensive computer testing, the vulnerability of the cervical spine, the asymmetry of muscles in the cervical spine, the predominance or lack of development of the muscular system are determined. Based on these indicators, the possible load is calculated and an individual training program is formed using innovative medical simulators. To treat and consolidate the result, you should take a course of 24 classes twice a year. The results of training on simulators are usually visible after 5-6 classes.

Conclusions: Thus, the signs of cervical osteochondrosis are often ignored or self-medicated. Meanwhile, this can lead to serious complications. A person is especially at risk in the case of self-treatment or the use of injuries of dangerous manual techniques and physical manipulations, which not only do not treat, but can further worsen the disease. It is better to entrust the treatment of cervical osteochondrosis to qualified specialists who will select for you gentle, modern and effective methods that exclude the possibility of injury to the affected cervical spine.

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